

Determining Senses for Word Sense Disambiguation in Turkish

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Abstract—Word sense disambiguation is an important intermediate stage for many natural language processing applications. The senses of an ambiguous word are the classification of usages for that specific word. This paper deals with the methodologies of determining the senses for a given word if they can not be obtained from an already available resource like WordNet. We offer a method that helps us to determine the sense boundaries gradually. In this method, first we decide on some features that are thought to be effective on the senses and divide the instances first into two, then according to the results of evaluations we continue dividing instances gradually. In a second method we use the pseudo words. We devise artificial words depending on some criteria and evaluate classification algorithms on these previously classified words.

Keywords—Word sense disambiguation, sense determination, pseudo words, sense granularity.

I. INTRODUCTION

UNDERSTANDING or interpreting the given text or discourse immediately is an incredible human capability. When we consider the children who acquire this ability at the very early ages, the task can be thought to be a very simple one that can be simulated by machines. However, natural languages are inherently ambiguous and difficult to be processed by computers. Having a better communication with the computers is, of course, not the major reason behind the researches about natural language processing (NLP); there are many other application areas such as text summarization, translation, information extraction, speech analysis and synthesis etc., where we need to understand text and discourse.

In [7] it has been expressed that the complexity of languages in a very nice way and emphasizes that the machines' inability to understand the information they hold restricts their usefulness and this is a bottleneck for the increasing amount of information kept in electronic format. This situation is not something due to the machines but complex structure of the natural languages.

When we are dealing with the complexity of languages, one of the difficulties we have to consider is the lexical ambiguity. This type of ambiguity which is an important problem at the bottom level of NLP applications does not have a perfect solution yet. Syntactic or semantic lexical ambiguity is the fundamental problem of NLP systems and disambiguation is necessary, or at least helpful, for many applications in one way or another as stated in [4]. The ultimate goal of the word sense disambiguation(WSD) researches which is an effort for solving lexical ambiguity is determining the most suitable sense of an ambiguous word among the possible set of senses for that specific word in a given text or discourse. This process is in fact classification of the ambiguous word in the given context. Memorandum [14] states the necessity of WSD in

machine translation and emphasizes that a word can be disambiguated whenever one can see N words on either side and deciding on this number N is the critical part of the task. This view formed the basic ideas of the WSD approaches. In fact, his point of view is only concerning one part of the fact, the meaning of the central word can be decided unambiguously if we are allowed to see N neighboring words, however the decision function does not solely depends on those N words in human language processing system. Additionally, there is even no consensus on the definition of a sense. The debates on this issue lead to a variety of perspectives in the history. Aristotle claims that words correspond to objects, thus meaning is independent of context. In [16] it has been emphasized that the usage rather than the meaning of the word and assumes that there are no predefined word senses, but usage of a word in a context determines meaning. Some others [2] believe that meaning is based on frequencies of words. And in [1] it has been thought that meaning of a word stems from its syntagmatic use in discourse. We believe in that the solution of all these discussions and the WSD process depends on understanding the human language processing system. In the following sections the problems and some possible solutions related to the sense classification of WSD, especially Turkish WSD, will be examined in a more detailed manner. The methods that can be used for sense classification of the words are discussed.

II. STEPS IN THE WSD PROCESS

Sense classification and granularity is one of the main problems in WSD, therefore the first step must be the determination of the set of applicable senses of a given word for a particular context. This set can be formed by using sources like dictionaries, thesauri, translation dictionaries etc. The next step will be the selection of features that can be helpful for resolving the ambiguity. Then the last step will be the determination of the most appropriate sense in the given context.

The lexical ambiguity may be either syntactic or semantic and resolving syntactic ambiguity is relatively easier than semantic ambiguity. In addition to these, determining the syntactic features that are affecting the sense classes is a very critical step in the WSD applications. Then the model that is formed by using this information needs to be tested by using computer programs.

In this stage, electronic resources that are available for the languages are the critical factors for the success of testing. Electronic dictionaries, thesari, bilingual corpora, parsers, morphological analyzers, ontologies like WordNet are the typical electronic resources that can be considered. Other than these, the structures of the specific languages must be taken into account, since the senses of a word and the factors that are

affecting sense distinctions vary dramatically in different languages.

The disambiguation process is a mapping function from a set of given features plus our general knowledge to the senses of the given word. The mapping function is very sensitive to the selected features and therefore precision and recall can be increased/ decreased depending on the features that are going to be used. One possible feature can be collocational words (e.g. *hoş* in hoş geldiniz-welcome or *karşı* in karşı geldi-he opposed). Other types of features can be the affixes, syntactic categories of the words preceding and succeeding the target word, POS etc. In our outgoing project we are trying to determine these effective features in WSD for Turkish.

The last item that must be thought is the evaluation process of the systems. There is no standard method for evaluating the successes of WSD applications, although there are some projects like SENSEVAL in the world.

III. APPLICATION

Electronic devices and computational methods have been improved dramatically in the last decades. These improvements had a positive effect on the computational linguistics area. Nowadays there are many electronic resources available that can be used for devising and testing different models. Turkish has very limited resources that can be used for these purposes. Electronic dictionaries are available for Turkish, but they have many inconsistencies especially in classifying the words into appropriate categories for different applications. Parsers, morphological analyzers and some other tools for Turkish language processing have been developed in recent years. However, some of them do not have a broad coverage or some others are not open to public. There are some ongoing projects for providing data for NLP applications in Turkish like METU Corpus Project [9].

The most frequently used disambiguation methods in WSD are supervised methods and we need a large coverage corpora in which different senses of the target word are annotated beforehand. The corpora must be used for training the computer programs and new corpora can be used to test the programs. There are available corpora for languages like English, Japanese, Spanish, etc especially in SENSEVAL project, but there is no corpus for Turkish yet. We are trying to build a corpus which has been sense tagged for a limited number of verbs and nouns. Evaluation process has the same type of problems; we need standardized corpora and methods for evaluation.

At the beginning, we have used seven stories from world classics¹. These stories are not annotated so we have annotated the senses of the verb *git* (to go), POS, affixes and collocations manually and applied Naive Bayes (NB) and Exemplar-based (EB) approaches for disambiguation [10]. However, manual annotation of all required information was a very time consuming task and the amount of data was very less than the required.

In the last quarter of 2003, METU Turkish corpus has become available for academic purposes. We have taken the

treebank part of the corpus. Treebank consists of parsed, morphologically analyzed and disambiguated sentences selected from the corpus. Not all the sentences in the corpus are included in the treebank, since the disambiguation process has to be achieved manually. The sentences are given in XML format and provide many syntactic features that can be helpful for disambiguation. It was the first time this treebank was open to academic researches, therefore, there were some errors and inconsistencies that had to be corrected manually. Moreover, sense tagging has to be achieved manually. We have selected a broader set of words and using only syntactic features that have been extracted from the sentences in which the target words occur.

A. Sense Determination

WSD applications basically have three steps as mentioned before, but researches mostly focused on the last two steps. The first step, determining the senses, is thought to be already achieved and the last two steps have been built on this assumption. However, having the predefined set of senses for a particular word is only possible for some certain languages. Languages such as English have electronic resources like WordNet and the senses of the words are given precisely as a result of many experts' efforts for many years. On the other hand, in many other languages there are no such resources or even no researches. Therefore, we need to find some methods for determining the "senses". The link between the word and the senses must be established carefully before going further.

We are using languages to communicate with each other and using the words in this communication. The words can be thought as the tools for referring to objects, relations and events in the world. If we think about the meaning of a word as the entity it refers to, there may be some problems. For example words co-referring to an entity may have a totally different meaning than the words themselves have. For example *üç* means three and *kağıt* means *paper* in Turkish. However, when they are used together "*üç kağıt*" means *trick* which is totally different than the two words.

Another candidate for the meaning of a word can be the dictionary definition given for that word. There may be a list of definitions that is applicable for a given word in a given dictionary, but this may not be the sense classification. For example in one of the Turkish dictionaries published by TDK the verb *gelmek* has 38 senses and in another Turkish dictionary written by [13] the same verb has 35 senses. Although the dictionaries are the first source for learning the meaning of a word they have many inconsistencies. It can be claimed that they are more accurate than any individual's knowledge of the meaning, but they are written depending on the people's usages and this is a contradiction. The dictionary definitions are also given by using some other words which causes circularity.

¹ Stories are: Gulliver, Candide, Ivan Nikiforovic, Tours Papazi, Mozart Prag Yolunda, Mektuplar, Kır Atlı.

TABLE I
TRANSLATIONS OF THREE SENSES OF TURKISH WORD "GELMEK" IN ENGLISH AND FRENCH

Lang.	Sense 1	Sense 2	Sense 3
Turkish	Varmak, geriye dönmek, gitmek (Ankara'ya geldim)	Çıkmak, getirilmiş olmak (Kahve Yemen'den gelirdi)	Peyda olmak (ona merak geldi)
English	to come	To originate, to come from	To appear, to happen
French	Venir, arriver	Venir de, sortir, provenir, être originaire, être apporté de	Venir, Se présenter à le'esprit

In Turkish there are many idioms, proverbs and compound words other than the normal usages and these types of usages make the sense classification task more complex. When the normal senses and these extra senses are considered together, for many words, the number of senses that are applicable become intractable. Furthermore, some of the word senses have no or very rare occurrences in the treebank.

It is very difficult to decide the number of senses and the distinctions between these senses for a given word. Senses are determined by their usages, cultures, time and domain of discourse etc. For example the word *gök* has senses like *sky*, *heavens*, *blue*, *not matured* but the usages of *blue*, *not matured* are very rare in contemporary Turkish, and the first two senses are used more frequently. The language has a dynamic structure and sometimes some new words/senses are being added or some old ones are forgotten.

These limitations enforced us to find some other ways for determining the senses of Turkish words. Our first attempt was obtaining the set of senses by grouping the senses given in the dictionaries and usages in the treebank. In this process we put the similar or related senses under the same sense class and ignored some of the rarely used ones. Unfortunately, the resulting set of senses, especially for some of the words were still intractable. As a second attempt, we thought that translations of the given words in other languages could be the candidates of the senses. But this approach had its own limitations and problems. Translations are one of the application areas of WSD, but it is not limited to this only, so this approach may not be suitable for some other applications. Moreover, one word may have different set of translations in different target languages as shown in Table I. Another problem is the usages that may not be translated reflecting the senses exactly to another language such as "*el koymak*" in Turkish means "*to confiscate*", although "*el*" means "*hand*" and "*koymak*" means "*to put*".

The next attempt for solving the sense determination problem is somehow a new approach. First we assumed two senses for the given word. The first sense was the most frequently used sense of the word and the second sense was the rest of the senses. Then according to this division, we evaluated our sentences. Then the senses were classified into three groups considering previous classification results. We continued in this way until obtaining an optimal set of senses

for the given word. The set of senses are found gradually and by using a trial-and-error approach. The usages and the occurrences of the senses are also considered for finding the optimal set of senses.

Pseudo words are used for overcoming the sense classification as the last attempt. All words have different meanings and if someone thinks about the word meanings in depth, one can notice an analogy between the two distinct words having two distinct or similar meanings and a single word having two distinct or similar senses. We want to emphasize that there are similarities how we assign meanings to two words and two senses. In Turkish we have a word root "*kara*" and this has different senses such as *black and land*. When we consider these two senses, there is no obvious correlation and it is easy to disambiguate the word *kara* in the given context. There are many other words that resemble this word in Turkish. We can simulate this type of word senses by some other words. For example we have the root words *haber (news)* and *ağaç (tree)* and these two words also do not have a direct relationship other than being a noun. If we produce an artificial word *haberağaç* and assign two senses to this synthetic word as *news* and *tree*, then this new word can have a similar functionality like our real word *kara*. In WSD we can use this idea just to obtain the sense tagged corpus for the next stages. All the sentences that have either *haber* or *ağaç* will be considered as the sentences that have the word *haberağaç* and the ones that have *haber* will be assigned a sense number as one indicating the first sense and the sentences that have *ağaç* will be assigned two in a similar fashion. Since we know which sentence have *haber* and which have *ağaç*, sense tagging will be completed easily and rapidly. These words were named as *pseudo words* in [5]. Although this approach has been known in the literature, there was not much work reported. In [3] Gaustad selected pseudo words randomly by considering POS and distribution and concluded no correlation between real words and pseudo words. A better set up has been used and word categories have been considered in [8]. The results are more accurate than the standard methods.

TABLE II
THE WORDS USED IN TESTS AND THEIR GROUPS

Pseudo words (The words that are loosely-coupled)		Pseudo words (The words that are tightly-coupled):		Real words (whose senses are loosely-coupled):		Real words (whose senses are tightly-coupled):		Gradual sense discrimination	
G1		G2		G3		G4		G5	
Test No	Words	Test No	Words	Test No	Words	Test No	Words	Test No	Words
T1	Acı-kız(1-2)	T6	Anne-baba-çocuk	T17	Kar(1-2-3)	T20	Çal(1-2-3)	T24	Yan1-2
Ratio/ #ex	0.32-0.81-0.12/ 43-108-17	Ratio/ #ex	0.31-0.29-0.4/ 98-91-124	Ratio/ #ex	0.24-0.57-0.19/ 4-11-3	Ratio/ #ex	0.61-0.110.28/ 27-4-12	Ratio/ #ex	0.13-0.87/ 17-118
T2	Anne-ses-gece	T7	Anne-baba	T18	Yüz(1-2-3-4)	T21	Hareket(1-2)	T25	Yan1.1-1.2-2
Ratio/ #ex	0.35-0.34-0.3/ 98-95-85	Ratio/ #ex	0.52-0.48/ 98-91	Ratio/ #ex	0.28-0.43-0.26- 0.03/ 33-50-30-3	Ratio/ #ex	0.86-0.14/ 29-4	Ratio/ #ex	0.07-0.07-0.86/ 8-9-118
T3	Yıl(1-3)- insan-göz	T8	Kadın-erkek	T19	Kız(1-2)	T22	Hava(1-2-3-4)	T26	Yan1-2-3
Ratio/ #ex	0.34-0.34- 0.02-0.3/ 138-138-8-120	Ratio/ #ex	0.67-0.33/ 153-75	Ratio/ #ex	0.9-0.1/ 113-12	Ratio/ #ex	0.37-0.21-0.26- 0.16/ 13-7-9-5	Ratio/ #ex	0.13-0.64-0.23/ 17-87-31
T4	Bugün-geyik- ülke	T9	Dün-yarın-bugün			T23	Yan(1.1-1.2-2-3- 4-5-7)	T27	Yan1-2-5-7
Ratio/ #ex	0.35-0.3-0.35/ 45-38-45	Ratio/ #ex	0.29-0.21-0.5/ 26-18-45			Ratio/ #ex	0.07-0.04-0.44- 0.23-0.04-0.13- 0.06/ 9-5-61-31-4-18-7	Ratio/ #ex	0.13-0.68-0.14- 0.06/ 17-93-18-7
T5	Kardeş-oda- sabah	T10	Sabah-aşam- gece					T28	Yan1-2-3-5-7
	0.34-0.36- 0.31/ 40-42-36	Ratio/ #ex	0.24-0.20-0.55/ 36-30-83					Ratio/ #ex	0.13-0.45-0.23- 0.14-0.06/ 17-62-31-18-7
		T11	Süre-saniye-saat						
			0.47-0.04-0.49/ 53-4-56						
		T12	Eski-yeni						
			0.36-0.64/ 43-78						
		T13	Ev-okul-park						
			0.71-0.12-0.17/ 195-33-45						
		T14	Köpek-geyik						
			0.49-0.51/ 36-38						
		T15	Vergi-para-faiz						
			0.3-0.44-0.27/ 29-43-26						
		T16	Peynir-ekmek- yemek						
			0.43-0.13-0.44/ 47-14-48						

TABLE III
TEST RESULTS (ACCURACY %)

Test No	AODE	KStar	J48
T1	77.97	80.35	78.57
T2	70.65	71.01	65.21
T3	72.77	73.51	75.49
T4	73.43	75.78	69.53
T5	73.72	70.33	66.94
T6	58.14	57.51	57.51
T 7	63.49	60.31	55.55
T 8	68.86	65.35	67.54
T 9	61.80	64.04	59.55
T 10	58.38	57.04	61.07
T 11	81.41	76.10	76.10
T 12	70.25	70.25	71.07
T 13	75.46	77.28	77.66
T 14	81.08	85.13	72.97
T 15	71.43	71.43	72.45
T 16	66.97	60.55	60.55
T 17	72.22	72.22	72.22
T 18	87.06	87.06	97.41
T 19	94.4	92.00	97.6
T 20	72.09	74.41	60.46
T 21	100	96.97	100
T 22	58.82	58.82	55.88
T 23	69.63	68.89	68.89
T 24	94.81	95.55	100
T 25	94.07	91.85	97.77
T 26	79.26	81.48	84.44
T 27	83.70	88.14	88.14
T 28	71.11	75.55	71.11

B. Experiments

We have used the WEKA system for testing. The implementations are in Java which is compatible with our previous applications and includes many famous machine learning algorithms. We have designed 28 data sets for testing all possible situations. These sets can be classified into five different experimental setups:

- Pseudo words (The words that are loosely-coupled): **G1**
- Pseudo words (The words that are tightly-coupled): **G2**
- Real words (whose senses are loosely-coupled): **G3**
- Real words (whose senses are tightly-coupled): **G4**
- Gradual sense discrimination: **G5**

Group G1 has 5, group G2 has 10, group G3 has 3, group G4 has 4, group G5 has 5 different sets in them. We have decided these numbers by considering the frequencies of the words in the corpus. The words in test sets are given in Table II. We have chosen three different types of machine learning algorithms to test our data. The algorithms are AODE, a statistical method that is an improved version of Naive-Bayes algorithm, KStar, an exemplar-based method, and J48, a decision tree method which is an improved version of C4.5. These algorithms have been applied to these sets and the results about the correctness are provided in Table III.

These results suggest that the selected algorithms performances are comparable. The correctness values must be considered in parallel with the distributions of the senses, since in some cases one sense can be dominant in the instances and baseline is higher for those words. Therefore, the absolute gain is the real accuracy value that has to be considered. For example in T21 the AODE algorithm gives 100% correct result, however, one of the senses has a distribution of 86% and the net gain is about 14%. On the other hand, for T17 the correctness value is 72.22% for the same algorithm, but the most frequent sense's ratio is 57% and the net gain is 15.22% leading to a better result from the previous one. As a result, distribution of senses and the correctness values must be interpreted together.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

WSD is an important problem in NLP systems. It has been investigated for many years; however there are still too many problems that have to be solved. First of all we need to find a model for the human language processing system. In order to do this we must have a coherent and plausible representation model for the entities in the world analogous to the humans. Sense classification and its representation in the human brain have to be explored. If this first and the most important step can be completed and the problems stated above for computational stage can be overcome then we can have a very powerful disambiguation system. Obtaining senses gradually or using pseudo words that can simulate the real ambiguous words can be solution for sense classification. For the pseudo words we have observed the followings:

- The distributions of the selected words have to be proportional or the correctness has to be measured relative to the distributions.
- The selected words must be unambiguous
- All possible occurrences of the real words have to be reflected by pseudo words like G1-G3, G2-G4 analogy
- The number of words in a pseudo word represents the number of senses of a real word, so any number of words can form a pseudo word for simulating more senses of real words.
- Some words have senses which can be disambiguated by POS. Pseudo words can be selected from different POS for representing this fact.

Gradual sense discrimination can be a solution for obtaining sense set of an ambiguous word that does not have a well defined set of senses by considering the usages in a given corpus.

REFERENCES

- [1] Barwise, J., and PERRY., J, 1983. Situations and Attitudes. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- [2] Bloomfield, L., 1933. Language. New York: Henry Holt.
- [3] Gaustad., T., 2001. Statistical Corpus-Based Word Sense Disambiguation: Pseudo words vs. Real Ambiguous Words., Proc. 39th Annual Meeting of ACL (ACL/EACL 2001) - Student Research Workshop.

- [4] IDE, N., and Veronis, J., 1998, Introduction to the special issue on word sense disambiguation: The State of the Art, Computational Linguistics, 24(1), 1-40.
- [5] Manning, C., Schütze, H., 1999. Foundations of Statistical Natural Language Processing, MIT Press. Cambridge, MA.
- [6] METU Turkish Treebank,
<http://www.ii.metu.edu.tr/~corpus/indextr.html>
- [7] MILLER, G., March 22, 2001, Ambiguous Words, iMP Magazine:
http://www.cisp.org/imp/march_2001/miller/03_01miller.htm
- [8] Nakov, P., and Hearst, M., 2003, Category-based Pseudo words, in the Companion Volume of the Proceedings of HLT-NAACL'03, pp. 67-69, Edmonton, Canada, May 2003.
- [9] Oflazer, K. Say, B., Hakkani-Tur, D.Z., Tur, G., 2003 Building a Turkish Treebank, Invited Chapter in Building and Exploiting Syntactically-Annotated Corpora, Anne Abeille Editor, Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- [10] Orhan, Z., Altan, Z., 2003, "Disambiguation of Turkish Word Senses By Supervised Statistical Methods", International XII. Turkish Symposium on Artificial Intelligence and Neural Networks (TAINN 2003).
- [11] Senseval, Evaluation exercises for Word Sense Disambiguation Organized by ACL-SIGLEX, <http://www.senseval.org>
- [12] TDK Turkish Dictionary, <http://tdk.org.tr/tdksozluk>
- [13] Tuğlaci, P., 1995, Okyanus Ansiklopedik Türkçe Sözlük, ABC Kitabevi Yayın ve dağıtım AŞ, İstanbul.
- [14] Weaver, W., 1949. Translation. Mimeographed, 12 pp., Reprinted in Locke, William N. and Booth, A. Donald (1955) (Eds.), Machine translation of languages. John Wiley & Sons, New York, 15-23.
- [15] WEKA: Data Mining Software in Java,
<http://www.cs.waikato.ac.nz/~ml/weka/index.html>
- [16] Wittgenstein L 1953, Philosophical Investigations translated by G E M Anscombe, Oxford: Basil Blackwell.